

Theories of Change and Strategy Development

Theories of Change as a Tool for Strategy Development and Performance Improvement in Research for Development Organizations

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Abstract

This paper looks at the role of a results-based management tool, namely theories of change, in strategy development for Research for Development organizations. The paper reviews the theoretical and empirical literature on strategy development and implementation, with a focus on strategic planning, strategic consensus and organizational performance. The role of theories of change in strategy development is analyzed using the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center, a research institution affiliated with the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research, as a case study. Theories of change were found to be a useful tool in strategy development, helping to align senior management vision with the rank-and-file understanding of the organization's objectives. The theories of change sessions also led to more creative and strategic thinking about key organizational issues.

Keywords

Strategy, strategy development, theory of change, research for development, agricultural research.

Article Title

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Introduction

This paper applies key concepts in the existing strategic management literature to a new setting, namely, Research for Development (R4D) organizations. Our main interest is to analyze the role of strategy development as an approach to improve organizational performance in the R4D context, which is not profit-driven and has intellectual capital as its main asset. Although the management literature abounds on the topic of business strategy and its link to organizational performance, no research has been undertaken in the context of R4D organizations. These organizations, whose core mandates focus on research excellence, have been evolving to respond to a changing donor landscape, where emphasis is increasingly put on results-based management and "development results." (Brignall, 2000; Kusek et al., 2001; Adams, 2002; Mosley et al., 2004; Holzapfel, 2014). Indeed, as early as 1999, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, through its Development Assistance Committee (an international forum of many of the largest funders of international aid with a mandate is to promote development co-operation in order to contribute to sustainable development and poverty alleviation), started to focus its program of work on results-based management (RBM) (Binnendijk, 2000).

RBM is an approach that aims to map out an organization's activities and how these contribute to its goals. It has a heavy focus on gathering evidence of results achieved, transparent reporting of said results for accountability purposes and continuous improvement (United Nations Development Group, 2007). In this paper, we argue that theories of change can be a useful RBM tool to improve organizational effectiveness and performance when used to inform the development of organizational strategy.

The first part of the paper provides a brief overview of the theoretical and empirical literature on strategy development and implementation. This is followed by a description of theories

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of change and their role in strategy development. A case study of the use of theories of change in the R4D context is then included. Finally, we offer concluding comments and outline key areas for future research to improve R4D organizational performance.

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Organization Strategy Development and Implementation

According to Steiner (1979), strategic planning is a formalized and systematic process by which an organization describes its purpose and detailed plans to meet it. Bateman and Zeithalm (1993) echo Steiner's view that strategic planning involves a systematic process for goal-setting and the prioritization of activities that an organization plans to undertake to meet objectives, thus providing a roadmap for its future. On the other hand, Henry Mintzberg, a leading strategic management academic likes to contrast strategic planning with the "art" of strategic crafting (Mintzberg, 1987). He argues that the orderly and systematic process of strategic planning described in most management textbooks is not reflective of the actual strategy development process in most organizations. In his view, the strategy development process is more akin to crafting, that is, it is organic and based on in-depth management experience and skill, requiring creativity and commitment.

The literature on the link between organizational strategy and firm performance dates back to the 1970's. The strategic management literature outlines many advantages of strategic planning. It is argued that the strategic planning process can improve how a firm allocates its resources (Quinn, 1980), help firms reposition or transform (Kotter, 1996), build a stronger market position and better address market uncertainty (Thompson et al., 2007). David (1997) contends that strategic planning puts organizations in a proactive position, enabling them to have a greater influence on, or better respond to, their external environment.

Viljoen and Dann (2000) see the main benefits of strategic planning as providing the broad direction to the organization, thus enabling improved resource allocation. Arasa and K'Obonyo (2012) help explain why strategic planning improves resource allocation: *"Managers are able to spend time, efforts and resources in activities that pay off... Individuals in an organization will strive to achieve clear objectives that are set"* (p. 204).

Earlier empirical studies that strove to examine the relationship between organizational strategy and firm performance found mixed results. Armstrong (1982), through a review of such studies, found that these failed to properly define key elements of the strategic planning process, which led to conflicting or inconclusive results. However, as researchers improved the definitional components of their empirical studies, clearer and more intuitive results started to emerge. For instance, Westgren et al. (1993), who focused on the agribusiness sector, found that the more comprehensive a firm's strategic planning process is, the higher it performs on various fronts, including in terms of its financial performance. Similarly, Baker and Leidecker (2001) reported a positive relationship between the use of formal strategic planning processes within firms and their financial performance. Dibrell and colleagues (2014) analyzed the relationship between the formal strategic planning process, planning flexibility, innovativeness and firm performance and found a positive relationship across firms in the natural resource, manufacturing and financial services sectors.

A key concept outlined in the literature is that of the "strategic consensus." Strategic consensus is a shared understanding of an organization's priorities across various levels therein (Homburg et al., 1999, Kellermanns et al., 2005). This shared understanding is said to lead to better coordinated efforts across the organization and therefore improved strategy implementation and ultimately, improved performance (Markóczy, 2001). This implies that the successful implementation of a strategy requires all actors within a firm to understand the underlying logic behind the strategy, its sub-elements and action plan (Dess, 1987).

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Floyd and Wooldridge (1992) assert that many senior executives complain that the strategies they develop often fail to be implemented properly across their organizations. The authors find that this is due to a poor understanding of the strategy by middle managers. A 2010 meta-analysis of the empirical literature on strategic consensus undertaken by Kellermanns and his colleagues finds that it indeed leads to improved organizational performance.

The empirical literature on strategic consensus, strategy development and performance focuses on firms, as opposed to other types of organizations that do not measure performance via a single easily measurable bottom line such as profit, such as R4D organizations, which strive to achieve multiple objectives such as research excellence, improved food security and reduced poverty, to name a few. Although performance in meeting these objectives is more complex, it can be argued that strategic consensus and the process of strategy development should also play an important role in driving performance.

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A theory of change describes the causal relationship between project or program activities and anticipated outcomes or impacts (Weiss, 1972). Shapiro (2005) sees theories of change as tools that enable to describe how change happens through a program intervention and how program implementation actions should lead to results. Serrat (2013) describes theories of change as models of the contribution of initiatives to intended results, made up of a logical chain of activities, outputs and outcomes. Patton (2008), Chen (2015), as well as Mayne (forthcoming), note the important difference between theories of change and other similar tools (for example, impact pathways, logic models), which is the inclusion of assumptions about the causal links between activities, outputs and outcomes.

As such, theories of change, if developed with input across the organization, can lead to an improved understanding of the organization's objectives, as well as the activities required to meet them, thus improving strategic consensus, which can in turn lead to better performance.

Theory to Practice: The Case of the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center

The International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center, henceforth referred to as CIMMYT (the Spanish acronym for Centro Internacional de Mejoramiento de Maíz y Trigo) is a research center headquartered in Mexico with offices throughout the developing world. CIMMYT works with partners worldwide to improve food security by raising productivity in maize and wheat cropping systems. CIMMYT is a member of the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR).

CIMMYT organized a set of five workshops from April to June 2015 to develop theories of change for its programming. The workshops had the following objectives:

- Establish a theory of change for each Flagship Projectⁱ through a participatory process
- Increase participants' awareness of results-based management
- Encourage sharing and learning across the organization

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The workshops participants were from all CIMMYT programs and ranged from relatively junior scientists to Program Director. Feedback from these workshops were also to be used to inform the development of the research strategies for CGIAR research programs focused on wheat and maize, as well as the development of the CIMMYT organizational strategy.

Workshop participants were presented with the following definition for theories of change to ensure that there was a common understanding of the task at hand:

- Presents a hypothetical identification of the ways by which change is expected to occur from output to outcome and impact.
- Questions the assumptions about causality underlying the relationships between outputs, outcomes and impact.
- Often used as a framework for testing hypotheses and incrementally building up the evidence base for the assumptions.
- It is a map that illustrates the relationship between actions and outcomes and also shows how outcomes are related to each other over the lifespan of the initiative/project/program.
- Includes impact / ultimate outcomes, intermediate outcomes, immediate outcomes, outputs, inputs, assumptions and risks.

Participants were also presented with the table below, which describes the terminology in the RBM literature and compares it with language used within the CGIAR system:

[INSERT TABLE 1 - TERMINOLOGY]

The CGIAR vision, mission and goals were then presented so that the theories of change could be aligned to the broader CGIAR Strategic Results Framework. Additional contextual information was also provided, including a list of key program beneficiaries and the current geographic focus of the programming. The CGIAR Strategic Results Framework was then presented and discussed, including its system-level outcomes (SLOs), intermediate development outcomes (IDOs) and sub-intermediate development outcomes (sub-IDOs). Participants were informed that SLOs were already aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, which were developed by national governments and by various international organizations.

The first task given to participants was to identify the key sub-IDOs for a given Flagship Project. To do so, each participant identified 2 to 3 sub-IDOs they thought represented the success of the given Flagship Project and wrote them down on sticky notes (one sub-IDO per sticky note). They then placed their sticky notes under the appropriate SLO that was marked on the conference room wall. Participants were then invited to review what was put on the wall as a group and refine the sticky note groupings together.

All participants were then tasked with identifying a small number of sub-IDOs relevant to the given Flagship Project and key cross-cutting sub-IDOs, using the three following steps:

1. Individually identifying 2 sub-IDOs they think represent the success of the Flagship Project and writing them down on sticky notes (one sub-IDO per sticky note).

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2. Placing their sub-IDs under the appropriate cross-cutting issue that was marked on the conference room wall.
3. Reviewing and refining as a group.

The following task for participants was to create the pathway of change by mapping backwards from the long-term outcome or impact. Participants were told that this was usually not a linear process and that depicting a reasonable and plausible storyline required taking three or four steps back, with the final step on the map reflecting the earliest outcomes.

It was explained to participants that outcome statements needed to include “who/what”, the change/desired effect (action verb), and a description of expected results. The following table was given as an example:

[INSERT TABLE 2 - OUTCOME STATEMENT EXAMPLE]

For the identification of the “who and what”, each participant identified two partners for direct interaction and for which the given Flagship Project can influence, as well as an outcome for each of the partners (that is, using an action verb to describe the change or desired effect in the expected results). This was followed by mapping actions or interventions associated with each of the outcomes, clearly differentiating between current and proposed interventions. As per the previous steps, a group discussion ensued to refine the language and logic.

The identification of assumptions and risks was the next task, where the group formulated statements about how and why they expected a set of outcomes to come about as depicted in the pathway of change, also explaining the contextual underpinnings of their statements, including beliefs and values. Internal and external risks (that is, elements that could undermine the success of a given Flagship Project) were then identified, along with the underlying assumptions. Again, this was reviewed and refined as a group.

Figure 1 below is one of the six theories of change developed, namely that of the Sustainable Intensification Flagship Project.

[INSERT FIGURE 1: GRAPHICAL REPRESENTATION OF THE THEORY OF CHANGE]

Table 3 outlines the assumptions and risks, as well interventions and outputs for each of the key elements of the Theory of Change above.

[INSERT TABLE 3: ASSUMPTIONS, RISKS, INTERVENTIONS AND OUTPUTS]

The last step was linking the theories of change to organizational strategy. This was done via small group discussion on the following questions:

- Are the clusters of activities (CoAs)ⁱⁱ as they stand today in line with the theory of change and are they the top R&D domains to achieve the theory of change?
- Are there any suggested changes to the CoAs structure? Is anything missing? Does anything seem non-essential?
- Are we working with the right partners? Are any new partnerships required?

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- Do we require new sources of funding to more effectively deliver?
- How will we set priorities among and within CoAs and/or research areas?
- Do we have all the information needed to make strategic decisions?
- What information is needed to prioritize R&D?
- What can we do to increase lateral learning?

This last step yielded a number of suggested changes to the Flagship Project and CoA structure, as well as several concrete ideas to improve partnerships, fundraising, marketing and the management of project-level and organizational risks. These suggestions and ideas were presented to CIMMYT senior management and are being integrated into the organizational strategy and implementation plan. Performance indicators will also be developed as a next step to ensure progress can be tracked at the project, program and institutional levels.

Conclusions

The use of theories of change to feed the strategy development process within CIMMYT can be considered a success on many fronts. The sessions offered researchers from across various programs and locations an opportunity to share information about their work and discuss how it fits within the overall organization and the broader CGIAR Strategic Results Framework. It also led to more creative and strategic thinking about key organizational issues, such as partnership building, fundraising, marketing and risk management. It can be expected, if results from the business literature on strategy development and strategic consensus can be generalized to R4D organizations, that the strategy implementation phase (to begin in 2016) will be more successful thanks to the inclusive approach used to develop the theories of change. This inclusive approach may also have positive impacts at the project level, where workshop participants may use their lessons learned to improve project planning, with better alignment with the Flagship Projects theories of change, the overall organizational strategy and the CGIAR Strategic Results Framework.

Further Research

There are several areas for further investigation in order to improve our understanding of the links between strategy development, strategic consensus and R4D organizational performance.

We have relied upon empirical evidence in the context of business management to posit that there is a link between strategic consensus, organizational strategy and performance in the R4D context. Empirically testing this hypothesis using appropriate metrics across various R4D organizations would enable to shed light on the extent to which lessons from the business literature are applicable to research organizations and other types of institutions not driven by profit maximization.

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Tables and Figures

Table 1 - Terminology

RBM Term	CGIAR Term	What it means
Inputs	Inputs	What you use to do the activities?
Outputs	Outputs	What demonstrates that you have done activities?
Immediate Outcomes (short term)	Research Outcomes	What happens as a result of what you have done?
Intermediate Outcomes (medium term)	Intermediate Development Outcomes	What happens next?
Impact / Ultimate Outcomes (long-term)	System-level Outcomes Sustainable Development Goals	Why are you doing this?

Table 2 - Outcome Statement Example

Who/What	Change/Desired Effect	In What
Farmers participating in program in Ethiopia	Increased adoption	New maize variety
Seed producers	Tested and promoted	Maize varieties with local farmers

Table 3 - Assumptions, Risks, Interventions and Outputs

Figure 1 - Graphical Representation of the Theory of Change

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ⁱ Flagship Projects are key components of CGIAR research programs, with each FP having specific objectives, outputs and outcomes, leading to specific Intermediate Development Outcomes.

ⁱⁱ Clusters of Activities are “structural components of a CRP flagship. They are the summary description of a range of products that are linked and related with each other e.g. through their contribution towards an outcome.”

<https://activities.ccafs.cgiar.org/ip/glossary.do>